

SOME PROPERTIES OF NEUTROSOPHIC CUBIC SOFT SETS

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Abstract:

The notion of Neutrosophic cubic soft sets P-union, P-intersection, are introduced and their related properties are investigated. We discussed about the internal and external neutrosophic cubic soft sets.

Key Words: Neutrosophic Cubic Soft Set, P-Union and P-Intersection & Internal and External Neutrosophic Cubic Soft Sets.

1. Introduction:

Neutrosophic set theory [5] extended the concept of cubic sets to the neutrosophic sets. They introduced the notions of truth-internal (indeterminacy-internal, falsity-internal) neutrosophic cubic sets and truth-external (indeterminacy-external, falsity-external) neutrosophic cubic sets and investigate related properties. In this paper , we introduced the definition of Neutrosophic cubic soft sets(NCSS)and proved some properties, We give a condition for the P-intersection of truth -external (resp. indeterminacy-external and falsity-external) neutrosophic cubic soft sets to be truth-external NCSS. We give an example to show that the P-union of falsity-external neutrosophic cubic soft sets may not be a NCSS. We provide a condition for the P-union of falsity-external (resp.indeterminacy-external and truth-external) neutrosophic cubic soft sets to be a falsity-external (resp. indeterminacy-external and truth-external) NCSS. Also we state the condition for the P-intersection of two neutrosophic cubic soft sets to be both a falsity-internal NCSS and a falsity external NCSS. We provide a condition for the P-union of two truth-external neutrosophic cubic soft sets to be a truth-internal NCSS.

2. Preliminaries:

Definition: 2.1

A pair $(\tilde{F}, I)$ is called cubic soft set over X if and only if $\tilde{F}$ is a mapping of $I(\subseteq E)$ into the set of all cubic sets in X, i.e., $\tilde{F} : I \rightarrow CP(X)$ where I is any subset of parameter’s set E, X is an initial universe set and $CP(X)$ is the collection of all cubic sets in X. Here we denote and define cubic soft set as $(\tilde{F}, I) = \tilde{F}(e_i) = \mathcal{A} = \{ \langle x, A_{e_i}(x), \lambda_{e_i}(x) \rangle; x \in X \}$ $e_i \in I$ in this set corresponding to each $e_i \in I$, $\mathcal{A} = \{ \langle x, A_{e_i}(x), \lambda_{e_i}(x) \rangle; x \in X \}$ is a cubic set in X in which $A_{e_i}(x)$ is an interval valued fuzzy set (briefly, an IVF set) and $\lambda_{e_i}(x)$ is a fuzzy set.

Definition: 2.2

Let X be a non-empty set. An interval neutrosophic set (INS) in X is a structure of the form:

$$\mathcal{A} = \{ \langle x, A_T(x), A_I(x), A_F(x) \rangle; x \in X \}$$

Where A_T , A_I and A_F are interval-valued fuzzy sets in X, which are called an interval truth membership function, an interval indeterminacy membership function and an interval falsity membership function, respectively.

Let X be a non-empty set. A neutrosophic cubic set (NCS) in X is a pair $\hat{A}=(\mathcal{A}, \Lambda)$ where $\mathcal{A} = \{ \langle x, A_T(x), A_I(x), A_F(x) \rangle; x \in X \}$ is an interval neutrosophic set in X and

$\Lambda = \{ \langle x, \lambda_T(x), \lambda_I(x), \lambda_F(x) \rangle; x \in X \}$ is a neutrosophic set in X.

Definition: 2.3

Let X be a non-empty set. A neutrosophic cubic set $\hat{A}=(\mathcal{A}, \Lambda)$ is said to be,

- ✓ truth-internal(briefly, T-internal) if the following inequality is valid $(x \in X)(A_T^-(x) \leq \lambda_T(x) \leq A_T^+(x))$,
- ✓ indeterminacy-internal(briefly, I-internal) if the following inequality is valid $(x \in X)(A_I^-(x) \leq \lambda_I(x) \leq A_I^+(x))$,
- ✓ falsity-internal(briefly, F-internal) if the following inequality is valid $(x \in X)(A_F^-(x) \leq \lambda_F(x) \leq A_F^+(x))$,

Definition: 2.4

Let X be a non-empty set. A neutrosophic cubic set $\hat{A}=(\mathcal{A}, \Lambda)$ is said to be,

- ✓ truth-external(briefly, T-external) if the following inequality is valid $(x \in X)(\lambda_T(x) \notin (A_T^-(x), A_T^+(x)))$.
- ✓ indeterminacy-external(briefly, I-external) if the following inequality is valid

$(x \in X)(\lambda_f(x) \notin (A_f^-(x), A_f^+(x)))$.

✓ falsity-external(briefly, F-external) if the following inequality is valid $(x \in X)(\lambda_f(x) \notin (A_f^-(x), A_f^+(x)))$.

Definition: 2.5

Let X be a non-empty set. A neutrosophic cubic soft set (NCSS) in X is a pair $(\tilde{F}, I) = \hat{A} = (\mathcal{A}, \Lambda)$ where, $\mathcal{A} = \{ \langle x, A_{T_{e_i}}(x), A_{I_{e_i}}(x), A_{F_{e_i}}(x) \rangle; x \in X \}$ is an interval neutrosophic soft set in X and $\Lambda = \{ \langle x, \lambda_{T_{e_i}}(x), \lambda_{I_{e_i}}(x), \lambda_{F_{e_i}}(x) \rangle; x \in X \}$ is a neutrosophic soft set.

Theorem: 2.6

Let $(\tilde{F}, I) = \hat{A}$ and $(\tilde{G}, J) = \hat{B}$ be T-external neutrosophic cubic soft sets in X such that,

$$\begin{aligned} & \max \{ \min \{ A_{T_{e_i}}^+(x), B_{T_{e_i}}^-(x) \}, \min \{ A_{T_{e_i}}^-(x), B_{T_{e_i}}^+(x) \} \} < (\lambda_{T_{e_i}} \wedge \psi_{T_{e_i}})(x) \\ & \leq \min \{ \max \{ A_{T_{e_i}}^+(x), B_{T_{e_i}}^-(x) \}, \max \{ A_{T_{e_i}}^-(x), B_{T_{e_i}}^+(x) \} \} \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

for all $x \in X$. Then $(\tilde{F}, I) \cap_p (\tilde{G}, J)$ is a T-external neutrosophic cubic soft set in X .

Proof:

Consider, $(\tilde{F}, I) \cap_p (\tilde{G}, J) = (\tilde{H}, C)$ where $C = I \cap J$

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{H}(e_i) &= \tilde{F}(e_i) && \text{if } e_i \in I - J \\ &= \tilde{G}(e_i) && \text{if } e_i \in J - I \\ &= \tilde{F}(e_i) \wedge_p \tilde{G}(e_i) && \text{if } e_i \in I \cap J. \end{aligned}$$

Where $\tilde{F}(e_i) \wedge_p \tilde{G}(e_i)$ is defined as,

$$\tilde{F}(e_i) \wedge_p \tilde{G}(e_i) = \{ \langle x, r \min \{ A_{T_{e_i}}(x), B_{T_{e_i}}(x) \}, (\lambda_{T_{e_i}} \wedge \psi_{T_{e_i}})(x) \rangle; x \in X \}; e_i \in I \cap J.$$

Take,

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha_{e_i} &= \min \{ \max \{ A_{T_{e_i}}^+(x), B_{T_{e_i}}^-(x) \}, \max \{ A_{T_{e_i}}^-(x), B_{T_{e_i}}^+(x) \} \} \\ \beta_{e_i} &= \max \{ \min \{ A_{T_{e_i}}^+(x), B_{T_{e_i}}^-(x) \}, \min \{ A_{T_{e_i}}^-(x), B_{T_{e_i}}^+(x) \} \} \end{aligned}$$

Then

$$\alpha_{e_i} = A_{T_{e_i}}^-(x), \alpha_{e_i} = B_{T_{e_i}}^-(x), \alpha_{e_i} = A_{T_{e_i}}^+(x) \text{ or } \alpha_{e_i} = B_{T_{e_i}}^+(x)$$

It is possible to consider, the cases $\alpha_{e_i} = A_{T_{e_i}}^-(x)$ and $\alpha_{e_i} = A_{T_{e_i}}^+(x)$ only because the remaining cases are similar to these cases, if $\alpha_{e_i} = A_{T_{e_i}}^-(x)$, then, $B_{T_{e_i}}^-(x) \leq B_{T_{e_i}}^+(x) \leq A_{T_{e_i}}^-(x) \leq A_{T_{e_i}}^+(x)$

Thus, $\beta_{e_i} = B_{T_{e_i}}^+(x)$, and so $B_{T_{e_i}}^-(x) = (A_{T_{e_i}} \cap B_{T_{e_i}})^-(x) \leq (A_{T_{e_i}} \cap B_{T_{e_i}})^+(x) = B_{T_{e_i}}^+(x) = \beta_{e_i} < (\lambda_{T_{e_i}} \wedge \psi_{T_{e_i}})(x)$

Hence, $(\lambda_{T_{e_i}} \wedge \psi_{T_{e_i}})(x) \notin ((A_{T_{e_i}} \cap B_{T_{e_i}})^-(x), (A_{T_{e_i}} \cap B_{T_{e_i}})^+(x))$

If $\alpha_{e_i} = A_{T_{e_i}}^+(x)$, then, $B_{T_{e_i}}^-(x) \leq A_{T_{e_i}}^+(x) \leq B_{T_{e_i}}^+(x)$ and thus

$\beta_{e_i} = \max \{ A_{T_{e_i}}^-(x), B_{T_{e_i}}^-(x) \}$ Suppose that, $\beta_{e_i} = A_{T_{e_i}}^-(x)$, then

$$B_{T_{e_i}}^-(x) \leq A_{T_{e_i}}^-(x) < (\lambda_{T_{e_i}} \wedge \psi_{T_{e_i}})(x) \leq A_{T_{e_i}}^+(x) \leq B_{T_{e_i}}^+(x) \quad (2)$$

It follows that,

$$B_{T_{e_i}}^-(x) \leq A_{T_{e_i}}^-(x) < (\lambda_{T_{e_i}} \wedge \psi_{T_{e_i}})(x) < A_{T_{e_i}}^+(x) \leq B_{T_{e_i}}^+(x) \quad (3)$$

Or

$$B_{T_{e_i}}^-(x) \leq A_{T_{e_i}}^-(x) < (\lambda_{T_{e_i}} \wedge \psi_{T_{e_i}})(x) = A_{T_{e_i}}^+(x) \leq B_{T_{e_i}}^+(x) \quad (4)$$

The case (3) induces a contradiction. The case (4) implies that,

$$(\lambda_{T_{e_i}} \wedge \psi_{T_{e_i}})(x) \notin ((A_{T_{e_i}} \cap B_{T_{e_i}})^-(x), (A_{T_{e_i}} \cap B_{T_{e_i}})^+(x))$$

Since

$$(\lambda_{T_{e_i}} \wedge \psi_{T_{e_i}})(x) = A_{T_{e_i}}^+(x) = (A_{T_{e_i}} \cap B_{T_{e_i}})^+(x)$$

Now, if $\beta_{e_i} = B_{T_{e_i}}^-(x)$, then $A_{T_{e_i}}^-(x) \leq B_{T_{e_i}}^-(x) < (\lambda_{T_{e_i}} \wedge \psi_{T_{e_i}})(x) \leq A_{T_{e_i}}^+(x) \leq B_{T_{e_i}}^+(x) \quad (5)$

Hence we have,

$$A_{T_{e_i}}^-(x) \leq B_{T_{e_i}}^-(x) < (\lambda_{T_{e_i}} \wedge \psi_{T_{e_i}})(x) < A_{T_{e_i}}^+(x) \leq B_{T_{e_i}}^+(x) \quad (6)$$

Or

$$A_{T_{e_i}}^-(x) \leq B_{T_{e_i}}^-(x) < (\lambda_{T_{e_i}} \wedge \psi_{T_{e_i}})(x) = A_{T_{e_i}}^+(x) \leq B_{T_{e_i}}^+(x) \quad (7)$$

The case (6) induces a contradiction. Then case (7) induces,

$$(\lambda_{T_{e_i}} \wedge \psi_{T_{e_i}})(x) \notin ((A_{T_{e_i}} \cap B_{T_{e_i}})^-(x), (A_{T_{e_i}} \cap B_{T_{e_i}})^+(x))$$

Consequently, we note that $(\tilde{F}, I) \cap_p (\tilde{G}, J)$ is an T-external neutrosophic cubic soft set in X .

Theorem: 2.7

Let $(\tilde{F}, I) = \hat{A}$ and $(\tilde{G}, J) = \hat{B}$ be F-external neutrosophic cubic soft sets in X such that,

$$\begin{aligned} & \max \{ \min \{ A_{F_{e_i}}^+(x), B_{F_{e_i}}^-(x) \}, \min \{ A_{F_{e_i}}^-(x), B_{F_{e_i}}^+(x) \} \} < (\lambda_{F_{e_i}} \wedge \psi_{F_{e_i}})(x) \\ & \leq \min \{ \max \{ A_{F_{e_i}}^+(x), B_{F_{e_i}}^-(x) \}, \max \{ A_{F_{e_i}}^-(x), B_{F_{e_i}}^+(x) \} \} \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

for all $x \in X$. Then $(\tilde{F}, I) \cap_p (\tilde{G}, J)$ is a F-external neutrosophic cubic soft set in X.

Proof:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Consider, } (\tilde{F}, I) \cap_p (\tilde{G}, J) &= (\tilde{H}, C) \text{ where } C = I \cap J \\ \tilde{H}(e_i) &= \tilde{F}(e_i) && \text{if } e_i \in I - J \\ &= \tilde{G}(e_i) && \text{if } e_i \in J - I \\ &= \tilde{F}(e_i) \wedge_p \tilde{G}(e_i) && \text{if } e_i \in I \cap J. \end{aligned}$$

Where $\tilde{F}(e_i) \wedge_p \tilde{G}(e_i)$ is defined as,

$$\tilde{F}(e_i) \wedge_p \tilde{G}(e_i) = \{ \langle x, r \min \{ A_{F_{e_i}}(x), B_{F_{e_i}}(x) \}, (\lambda_{F_{e_i}}(x) \wedge \psi_{F_{e_i}}(x)) \rangle : x \in X \}, e_i \in I \cap J.$$

Take, $\alpha_{e_i} = \min \{ \max \{ A_{F_{e_i}}^+(x), B_{F_{e_i}}^-(x) \}, \max \{ A_{F_{e_i}}^-(x), B_{F_{e_i}}^+(x) \} \}$

$$\beta_{e_i} = \max \{ \min \{ A_{F_{e_i}}^+(x), B_{F_{e_i}}^-(x) \}, \min \{ A_{F_{e_i}}^-(x), B_{F_{e_i}}^+(x) \} \}$$

Then $\alpha_{e_i} = A_{F_{e_i}}^-(x)$, $\alpha_{e_i} = B_{F_{e_i}}^-(x)$, $\alpha_{e_i} = A_{F_{e_i}}^+(x)$ or $\alpha_{e_i} = B_{F_{e_i}}^+(x)$

It is possible to consider, the cases $\alpha_{e_i} = A_{F_{e_i}}^-(x)$ and $\alpha_{e_i} = A_{F_{e_i}}^+(x)$ only because the remaining cases are similar to these cases, if $\alpha_{e_i} = A_{F_{e_i}}^-(x)$, then $B_{F_{e_i}}^-(x) \leq B_{F_{e_i}}^+(x) \leq A_{F_{e_i}}^-(x) \leq A_{F_{e_i}}^+(x)$

Thus, $\beta_{e_i} = B_{F_{e_i}}^+(x)$, and so, $B_{F_{e_i}}^-(x) = (A_{F_{e_i}} \cap B_{F_{e_i}})^-(x) \leq (A_{F_{e_i}} \cap B_{F_{e_i}})^+(x) = B_{F_{e_i}}^+(x) = \beta_{e_i} < (\lambda_{F_{e_i}} \wedge \psi_{F_{e_i}})(x)$

Hence, $(\lambda_{F_{e_i}} \wedge \psi_{F_{e_i}})(x) \notin ((A_{F_{e_i}} \cap B_{F_{e_i}})^-(x), (A_{F_{e_i}} \cap B_{F_{e_i}})^+(x))$

If $\alpha_{e_i} = A_{F_{e_i}}^+(x)$, then, $B_{F_{e_i}}^-(x) \leq A_{F_{e_i}}^+(x) \leq B_{F_{e_i}}^+(x)$ and thus,

$\beta_{e_i} = \max \{ A_{F_{e_i}}^-(x), B_{F_{e_i}}^-(x) \}$ Suppose that, $\beta_{e_i} = A_{F_{e_i}}^-(x)$ then,

$$B_{F_{e_i}}^-(x) \leq A_{F_{e_i}}^-(x) < (\lambda_{F_{e_i}} \wedge \psi_{F_{e_i}})(x) \leq A_{F_{e_i}}^+(x) \leq B_{F_{e_i}}^+(x) \quad (2)$$

It follows that,

$$B_{F_{e_i}}^-(x) \leq A_{F_{e_i}}^-(x) < (\lambda_{F_{e_i}} \wedge \psi_{F_{e_i}})(x) < A_{F_{e_i}}^+(x) \leq B_{F_{e_i}}^+(x) \quad (3)$$

Or

$$B_{F_{e_i}}^-(x) \leq A_{F_{e_i}}^-(x) < (\lambda_{F_{e_i}} \wedge \psi_{F_{e_i}})(x) = A_{F_{e_i}}^+(x) \leq B_{F_{e_i}}^+(x) \quad (4)$$

The case (3) induces a contradiction. The case (4) implies that,

$$(\lambda_{F_{e_i}} \wedge \psi_{F_{e_i}})(x) \notin ((A_{F_{e_i}} \cap B_{F_{e_i}})^-(x), (A_{F_{e_i}} \cap B_{F_{e_i}})^+(x))$$

Since $(\lambda_{F_{e_i}} \wedge \psi_{F_{e_i}})(x) = A_{F_{e_i}}^+(x) = (A_{F_{e_i}} \cap B_{F_{e_i}})^+(x)$

Now, if $\beta_{e_i} = B_{F_{e_i}}^-(x)$ then $A_{F_{e_i}}^-(x) \leq B_{F_{e_i}}^-(x) < (\lambda_{F_{e_i}} \wedge \psi_{F_{e_i}})(x) \leq A_{F_{e_i}}^+(x) \leq B_{F_{e_i}}^+(x) \quad (5)$

Hence we have,

$$A_{F_{e_i}}^-(x) \leq B_{F_{e_i}}^-(x) < (\lambda_{F_{e_i}} \wedge \psi_{F_{e_i}})(x) < A_{F_{e_i}}^+(x) \leq B_{F_{e_i}}^+(x) \quad (6)$$

Or

$$A_{F_{e_i}}^-(x) \leq B_{F_{e_i}}^-(x) < (\lambda_{F_{e_i}} \wedge \psi_{F_{e_i}})(x) = A_{F_{e_i}}^+(x) \leq B_{F_{e_i}}^+(x) \quad (7)$$

The case (6) induces a contradiction. Then case (7) induces,

$$(\lambda_{F_{e_i}} \wedge \psi_{F_{e_i}})(x) \notin ((A_{F_{e_i}} \cap B_{F_{e_i}})^-(x), (A_{F_{e_i}} \cap B_{F_{e_i}})^+(x))$$

Consequently, we note that $(\tilde{F}, I) \cap_p (\tilde{G}, J)$ is an F-external neutrosophic cubic soft set in X.

Similarly we have the following theorem.

Theorem: 2.8

Let $(\tilde{F}, I) = \hat{A}$ and $(\tilde{G}, J) = \hat{B}$ be I-external neutrosophic cubic soft sets in X such that,

$$\begin{aligned} &\max \{ \min \{ A_{I_{e_i}}^+(x), B_{I_{e_i}}^-(x) \}, \min \{ A_{I_{e_i}}^-(x), B_{I_{e_i}}^+(x) \} \} < (\lambda_{I_{e_i}} \wedge \psi_{I_{e_i}})(x) \\ &\leq \min \{ \max \{ A_{I_{e_i}}^+(x), B_{I_{e_i}}^-(x) \}, \max \{ A_{I_{e_i}}^-(x), B_{I_{e_i}}^+(x) \} \} \end{aligned}$$

for all $x \in X$. Then $(\tilde{F}, I) \cap_p (\tilde{G}, J)$ is a I-external neutrosophic cubic soft set in X.

Example: 2.9

Let $(\tilde{F}, I) = \hat{A}$ and $(\tilde{G}, J) = \hat{B}$ be I-external neutrosophic cubic soft sets in X = [0,1] with the tabular representations in Tables 1 and 2, respectively,

Table 1: Tabular representation of $(\mathcal{A}, \Lambda) = \hat{A}$

X	$\mathcal{A}_{e_1}(x)$	$\Lambda_{e_1}(x)$
$0 \leq x \leq 0.5$	([0.25,0.26],[0.2,0.3],[0.15,0.25])	(0.25,0.15,0.5x+0.5)
$0.5 \leq x \leq 1$	([0.5,0.7],[0.5,0.6],[0.6,0.7])	(0.55,0.75,0.30)

$0 \leq x \leq 0.3$	$([0.1,0.15],[0.2,0.25],[0.15,0.25])$	$(0.25,0.15,0.1x+0.1)$
$0.3 \leq x \leq 1$	$([0.1,0.2],[0.7,0.8],[0.6,0.7])$	$(0.55,0.70,0.30)$

X	$\mathcal{A}_{e2}(x)$	$\Lambda_{e2}(x)$
$0 \leq x \leq 0.7$	$([0.25,0.26],[0.2,0.5],[0.15,0.35])$	$(0.25,0.45,0.7)$
$0.7 \leq x \leq 1$	$([0.7,0.8],[0.7,0.75],[0.8,0.9])$	$(0.8,0.85,0.92)$
$0 \leq x \leq 0.5$	$([0.25,0.26],[0.2,0.3],[0.15,0.25])$	$(0.25,0.15,0.5x+0.5)$
$0.5 \leq x \leq 1$	$([0.5,0.7],[0.5,0.6],[0.6,0.7])$	$(0.55,0.70,0.30)$

Table 2: Tabular representation of $(\mathfrak{B}, \psi) = \tilde{B}$

X	$\mathfrak{B}_{e1}(x)$	$\Psi_{e1}(x)$
$0 \leq x \leq 0.5$	$([0.25,0.26],[0.2,0.3],[0.8,0.9])$	$(0.25,0.15,0.40)$
$0.5 \leq x \leq 1$	$([0.5,0.7],[0.5,0.6],[0.1,0.2])$	$(0.55,0.75, x)$
$0 \leq x \leq 0.3$	$([0.1,0.15],[0.2,0.25],[0.15,0.28])$	$(0.25,0.15,0.1x+0.1)$
$0.3 \leq x \leq 1$	$([0.1,0.2],[0.7,0.8],[0.7,0.8])$	$(0.55,0.70,0.40)$

X	$\mathfrak{B}_{e2}(x)$	$\Psi_{e2}(x)$
$0 \leq x \leq 0.7$	$([0.25,0.26],[0.2,0.5],[0.25,0.35])$	$(0.25,0.45,0.7)$
$0.7 \leq x \leq 1$	$([0.7,0.8],[0.7,0.75],[0.8,0.92])$	$(0.8,0.85,0.92)$
$0 \leq x \leq 0.5$	$([0.25,0.26],[0.2,0.3],[0.18,0.30])$	$(0.25,0.15,0.5x+0.5)$
$0.5 \leq x \leq 1$	$([0.5,0.7],[0.5,0.6],[0.7,0.8])$	$(0.55,0.75,0.85)$

X	$(\mathcal{A}_{e1} \cup \mathfrak{B}_{e1})(x)$	$(\Lambda_{e1} \cup \Psi_{e1})(x)$
$0 \leq x \leq 0.5$	$([0.25,0.26],[0.2,0.3],[0.8,0.9])$	$(0.25,0.15,0.5x+0.5)$
$0.5 \leq x \leq 1$	$([0.5,0.7],[0.5,0.6],[0.6,0.7])$	$(0.55,0.75, x)$
$0 \leq x \leq 0.3$	$([0.1,0.15],[0.2,0.25],[0.15,0.28])$	$(0.25,0.15,0.1x+0.1)$
$0.3 \leq x \leq 1$	$([0.1,0.2],[0.7,0.8],[0.7,0.8])$	$(0.55,0.70,0.40)$

X	$(\mathcal{A}_{e2} \cup \mathfrak{B}_{e2})(x)$	$(\Lambda_{e2} \cup \Psi_{e2})(x)$
$0 \leq x \leq 0.7$	$([0.25,0.26],[0.2,0.5],[0.25,0.35])$	$(0.25,0.45,0.7)$
$0.7 \leq x \leq 1$	$([0.7,0.8],[0.7,0.75],[0.8,0.92])$	$(0.8,0.85,0.92)$
$0 \leq x \leq 0.5$	$([0.25,0.26],[0.2,0.3],[0.18,0.30])$	$(0.25,0.15,0.5x+0.5)$
$0.5 \leq x \leq 1$	$([0.5,0.7],[0.5,0.6],[0.7,0.8])$	$(0.55,0.75,0.85)$

Then, $(\lambda_{F_{e1}} \vee \psi_{F_{e1}}) = 0.67 \in (0.67,0.7) = (A_{F_{e1}} \cup B_{F_{e1}})^-(0.67), (A_{F_{e1}} \cup B_{F_{e1}})^+(0.67)$

$(\lambda_{F_{e1}} \vee \psi_{F_{e1}}) = 0.78 \in (0.7,0.8) = (A_{F_{e1}} \cup B_{F_{e1}})^-(0.78), (A_{F_{e1}} \cup B_{F_{e1}})^+(0.78)$

$(\lambda_{F_{e2}} \vee \psi_{F_{e2}}) = 0.82 \in (0.8,0.9) = (A_{F_{e2}} \cup B_{F_{e2}})^-(0.82), (A_{F_{e2}} \cup B_{F_{e2}})^+(0.82)$

$(\lambda_{F_{e2}} \vee \psi_{F_{e2}}) = 0.78 \in (0.7,0.8) = (A_{F_{e2}} \cup B_{F_{e2}})^-(0.78), (A_{F_{e2}} \cup B_{F_{e2}})^+(0.78)$

and so the P-union $(\tilde{F}, I) \cup_p (\tilde{G}, J) = (\mathcal{A} \cup \mathfrak{B}, \Lambda \cup \Psi)$ is not an F-external neutrosophic cubic soft set in $X=[0,1]$.

Theorem: 2.10

Let $(\tilde{F}, I) = \tilde{A}$ and $(\tilde{G}, J) = \tilde{B}$ be F-external neutrosophic cubic soft sets in X such that,

$$\begin{aligned} \max \{ \min \{ A_{F_{e1}}^+(x), B_{F_{e1}}^-(x) \}, \min \{ A_{F_{e1}}^-(x), B_{F_{e1}}^+(x) \} \} &\leq (\lambda_{F_{e1}} \wedge \psi_{F_{e1}})(x) \\ &< \min \{ \max \{ A_{F_{e1}}^+(x), B_{F_{e1}}^-(x) \}, \max \{ A_{F_{e1}}^-(x), B_{F_{e1}}^+(x) \} \} \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

for all $x \in X$. Then $(\tilde{F}, I) \cup_p (\tilde{G}, J)$ is a F-external neutrosophic cubic soft set in X.

Proof:

Consider, $(\tilde{F}, I) \cup_p (\tilde{G}, J) = (\tilde{H}, C)$ where $C = I \cup J$

$$\begin{aligned}\tilde{H}(e_i) &= \tilde{F}(e_i) && \text{if } e_i \in I - J \\ &= \tilde{G}(e_i) && \text{if } e_i \in J - I \\ &= \tilde{F}(e_i) \vee_p \tilde{G}(e_i) && \text{if } e_i \in I \cap J.\end{aligned}$$

Where $\tilde{F}(e_i) \vee_p \tilde{G}(e_i)$ is defined as,

$$\tilde{F}(e_i) \vee_p \tilde{G}(e_i) = \{ \langle x, r \max \{A_{F_{e_i}}(x), B_{F_{e_i}}(x)\}, (\lambda_{F_{e_i}}(x) \vee \psi_{F_{e_i}}(x)) \rangle : x \in X \}, e_i \in I \cap J.$$

Take, $\alpha_{e_i} = \min \{ \max \{A_{F_{e_i}}^+(x), B_{F_{e_i}}^-(x)\}, \max \{A_{F_{e_i}}^-(x), B_{F_{e_i}}^+(x)\} \}$

$$\beta_{e_i} = \max \{ \min \{A_{F_{e_i}}^+(x), B_{F_{e_i}}^-(x)\}, \min \{A_{F_{e_i}}^-(x), B_{F_{e_i}}^+(x)\} \}$$

Then $\alpha_{e_i} = A_{F_{e_i}}^-(x)$, $\alpha_{e_i} = B_{F_{e_i}}^-(x)$, $\alpha_{e_i} = A_{F_{e_i}}^+(x)$ or $\alpha_{e_i} = B_{F_{e_i}}^+(x)$

It is possible to consider, the cases $\alpha_{e_i} = A_{F_{e_i}}^-(x)$ and $\alpha_{e_i} = A_{F_{e_i}}^+(x)$ only because the remaining cases are similar to these cases, if $\alpha_{e_i} = A_{F_{e_i}}^-(x)$ then, $B_{F_{e_i}}^-(x) \leq B_{F_{e_i}}^+(x) \leq A_{F_{e_i}}^-(x) \leq A_{F_{e_i}}^+(x)$

Thus, $\beta_{e_i} = B_{F_{e_i}}^+(x)$, and so $B_{F_{e_i}}^-(x) = (A_{F_{e_i}} \cup B_{F_{e_i}})^-(x) = A_{F_{e_i}}^-(x) = \alpha_{e_i} > (\lambda_{F_{e_i}} \vee \psi_{F_{e_i}})(x)$

Hence, $(\lambda_{F_{e_i}} \vee \psi_{F_{e_i}})(x) \notin ((A_{F_{e_i}} \cup B_{F_{e_i}})^-(x), (A_{F_{e_i}} \cup B_{F_{e_i}})^+(x))$

If $\alpha_{e_i} = A_{F_{e_i}}^+(x)$, then, $B_{F_{e_i}}^-(x) \leq A_{F_{e_i}}^+(x) \leq B_{F_{e_i}}^+(x)$ and thus

$\beta_{e_i} = \max \{A_{F_{e_i}}^-(x), B_{F_{e_i}}^-(x)\}$ Suppose that, $\beta_{e_i} = A_{F_{e_i}}^-(x)$ then

$$B_{F_{e_i}}^-(x) \leq A_{F_{e_i}}^-(x) < (\lambda_{F_{e_i}} \vee \psi_{F_{e_i}})(x) \leq A_{F_{e_i}}^+(x) \leq B_{F_{e_i}}^+(x) \quad (2)$$

It follows that,

$$B_{F_{e_i}}^-(x) \leq A_{F_{e_i}}^-(x) < (\lambda_{F_{e_i}} \vee \psi_{F_{e_i}})(x) < A_{F_{e_i}}^+(x) \leq B_{F_{e_i}}^+(x) \quad (3)$$

Or

$$B_{F_{e_i}}^-(x) \leq A_{F_{e_i}}^-(x) = (\lambda_{F_{e_i}} \vee \psi_{F_{e_i}})(x) < A_{F_{e_i}}^+(x) \leq B_{F_{e_i}}^+(x) \quad (4)$$

The case (3) induces a contradiction. The case (4) implies that, $(\lambda_{F_{e_i}} \vee \psi_{F_{e_i}})(x) \notin ((A_{F_{e_i}} \cup B_{F_{e_i}})^-(x), (A_{F_{e_i}} \cup B_{F_{e_i}})^+(x))$

Since $(\lambda_{F_{e_i}} \vee \psi_{F_{e_i}})(x) = A_{F_{e_i}}^-(x) = (A_{F_{e_i}} \cup B_{F_{e_i}})^-(x)$

Now, if $\beta_{e_i} = B_{F_{e_i}}^-(x)$ then, $A_{F_{e_i}}^-(x) \leq B_{F_{e_i}}^-(x) \leq (\lambda_{F_{e_i}} \vee \psi_{F_{e_i}})(x) \leq A_{F_{e_i}}^+(x) \leq B_{F_{e_i}}^+(x) \quad (5)$

Hence we have,

$$A_{F_{e_i}}^-(x) \leq B_{F_{e_i}}^-(x) < (\lambda_{F_{e_i}} \vee \psi_{F_{e_i}})(x) \leq A_{F_{e_i}}^+(x) \leq B_{F_{e_i}}^+(x) \quad (6)$$

Or

$$A_{F_{e_i}}^-(x) \leq B_{F_{e_i}}^-(x) = (\lambda_{F_{e_i}} \vee \psi_{F_{e_i}})(x) \leq A_{F_{e_i}}^+(x) \leq B_{F_{e_i}}^+(x) \quad (7)$$

The case (6) induces a contradiction. Then case (7) induces,

$$(\lambda_{F_{e_i}} \vee \psi_{F_{e_i}})(x) \notin ((A_{F_{e_i}} \cup B_{F_{e_i}})^-(x), (A_{F_{e_i}} \cup B_{F_{e_i}})^+(x))$$

Consequently, we note that $(\tilde{F}, I) \cup_p (\tilde{G}, J)$ is an F-external neutrosophic cubic soft set in X.

Similarly we have the following theorems.

Theorem: 2.11

Let $(\tilde{F}, I) = \hat{A}$ and $(\tilde{G}, J) = \hat{B}$ be T-external neutrosophic cubic soft sets in X such that,

$$\begin{aligned}\max \{ \min \{A_{T_{e_i}}^+(x), B_{T_{e_i}}^-(x)\}, \min \{A_{T_{e_i}}^-(x), B_{T_{e_i}}^+(x)\} \} &\leq (\lambda_{T_{e_i}} \vee \psi_{T_{e_i}})(x) \\ &< \min \{ \max \{A_{T_{e_i}}^+(x), B_{T_{e_i}}^-(x)\}, \max \{A_{T_{e_i}}^-(x), B_{T_{e_i}}^+(x)\} \}\end{aligned}$$

For all $x \in X$. Then $(\tilde{F}, I) \cup_p (\tilde{G}, J)$ is a T-external neutrosophic cubic soft set in X.

Theorem: 2.12

Let $(\tilde{F}, I) = \hat{A}$ and $(\tilde{G}, J) = \hat{B}$ be I-external neutrosophic cubic soft sets in X such that,

$$\begin{aligned}\max \{ \min \{A_{I_{e_i}}^+(x), B_{I_{e_i}}^-(x)\}, \min \{A_{I_{e_i}}^-(x), B_{I_{e_i}}^+(x)\} \} &\leq (\lambda_{I_{e_i}} \vee \psi_{I_{e_i}})(x) \\ &< \min \{ \max \{A_{I_{e_i}}^+(x), B_{I_{e_i}}^-(x)\}, \max \{A_{I_{e_i}}^-(x), B_{I_{e_i}}^+(x)\} \}\end{aligned}$$

For all $x \in X$. Then $(\tilde{F}, I) \cup_p (\tilde{G}, J)$ is an I-external neutrosophic cubic soft set in X.

Theorem: 2.13

Let $(\tilde{F}, I) = \hat{A}$ and $(\tilde{G}, J) = \hat{B}$ are neutrosophic cubic soft sets in X satisfy the following condition,

$$\begin{aligned}\min \{ \max \{A_{F_{e_i}}^+(x), B_{F_{e_i}}^-(x)\}, \max \{A_{F_{e_i}}^-(x), B_{F_{e_i}}^+(x)\} \} &= (\lambda_{F_{e_i}} \wedge \psi_{F_{e_i}})(x) \\ &= \max \{ \min \{A_{F_{e_i}}^+(x), B_{F_{e_i}}^-(x)\}, \min \{A_{F_{e_i}}^-(x), B_{F_{e_i}}^+(x)\} \}\end{aligned}$$

For all $x \in X$. Then $(\tilde{F}, I) \cap_p (\tilde{G}, J)$ of $(\tilde{F}, I) = \hat{A}$ and $(\tilde{G}, J) = \hat{B}$ is both F-internal neutrosophic cubic soft set and F-external neutrosophic cubic soft set in X.

Proof:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Consider, } (\tilde{F}, I) \cap_p (\tilde{G}, J) &= (\tilde{H}, C) \text{ where } C = I \cap J \\ \tilde{H}(e_i) &= \tilde{F}(e_i) \quad \text{if } e_i \in I - J \\ &= \tilde{G}(e_i) \quad \text{if } e_i \in J - I \\ &= \tilde{F}(e_i) \wedge_p \tilde{G}(e_i) \quad \text{if } e_i \in I \cap J. \end{aligned}$$

Where $\tilde{F}(e_i) \wedge_p \tilde{G}(e_i)$ is defined as,

$$\tilde{F}(e_i) \wedge_p \tilde{G}(e_i) = \{ \langle x, r \min \{ A_{F_{e_i}}^+(x), B_{F_{e_i}}^-(x) \}, (\lambda_{F_{e_i}}(x) \wedge \psi_{F_{e_i}}(x)) \rangle : x \in X \}, e_i \in I \cap J.$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Take, } \alpha_{e_i} &= \min \{ \max \{ A_{F_{e_i}}^+(x), B_{F_{e_i}}^-(x) \}, \max \{ A_{F_{e_i}}^-(x), B_{F_{e_i}}^+(x) \} \} \\ \beta_{e_i} &= \max \{ \min \{ A_{F_{e_i}}^+(x), B_{F_{e_i}}^-(x) \}, \min \{ A_{F_{e_i}}^-(x), B_{F_{e_i}}^+(x) \} \} \end{aligned}$$

Then $\alpha_{e_i} = A_{F_{e_i}}^-(x)$, $\alpha_{e_i} = B_{F_{e_i}}^-(x)$, $\alpha_{e_i} = A_{F_{e_i}}^+(x)$ or $\alpha_{e_i} = B_{F_{e_i}}^+(x)$

It is possible to consider, the cases $\alpha_{e_i} = A_{F_{e_i}}^-(x)$ and $\alpha_{e_i} = A_{F_{e_i}}^+(x)$ only because the remaining cases are similar to these cases, if $\alpha_{e_i} = A_{F_{e_i}}^-(x)$, then, $B_{F_{e_i}}^-(x) \leq B_{F_{e_i}}^+(x) \leq A_{F_{e_i}}^-(x) \leq A_{F_{e_i}}^+(x)$

Thus, $\beta_{e_i} = B_{F_{e_i}}^+(x)$, and so, $A_{F_{e_i}}^-(x) = \alpha_{e_i} = (\lambda_{F_{e_i}} \wedge \psi_{F_{e_i}})(x) = \beta_{e_i} = B_{F_{e_i}}^+(x)$

Hence, $B_{F_{e_i}}^-(x) \leq B_{F_{e_i}}^+(x) = (\lambda_{F_{e_i}} \wedge \psi_{F_{e_i}})(x) = A_{F_{e_i}}^-(x) \leq A_{F_{e_i}}^+(x)$

Which implies that, $(\lambda_{F_{e_i}} \wedge \psi_{F_{e_i}})(x) = B_{F_{e_i}}^+(x) = (A_{F_{e_i}} \cap B_{F_{e_i}})^+(x)$

Hence, $(\lambda_{F_{e_i}} \wedge \psi_{F_{e_i}})(x) \notin ((A_{F_{e_i}} \cap B_{F_{e_i}})^-(x), (A_{F_{e_i}} \cap B_{F_{e_i}})^+(x))$

And $(A_{F_{e_i}} \cap B_{F_{e_i}})^-(x) \leq (\lambda_{F_{e_i}} \wedge \psi_{F_{e_i}})(x) \leq (A_{F_{e_i}} \cap B_{F_{e_i}})^+(x)$

If $\alpha_{e_i} = A_{F_{e_i}}^+(x)$, then, $B_{F_{e_i}}^-(x) \leq A_{F_{e_i}}^+(x) \leq B_{F_{e_i}}^+(x)$ and thus, $(\lambda_{F_{e_i}} \wedge \psi_{F_{e_i}})(x) = A_{F_{e_i}}^+(x) = (A_{F_{e_i}} \cap B_{F_{e_i}})^+(x)$

Hence, $(\lambda_{F_{e_i}} \wedge \psi_{F_{e_i}})(x) \notin ((A_{F_{e_i}} \cap B_{F_{e_i}})^-(x), (A_{F_{e_i}} \cap B_{F_{e_i}})^+(x))$

And $(A_{F_{e_i}} \cap B_{F_{e_i}})^-(x) \leq (\lambda_{F_{e_i}} \wedge \psi_{F_{e_i}})(x) \leq (A_{F_{e_i}} \cap B_{F_{e_i}})^+(x)$

Consequently,

$(\tilde{F}, I) \cap_p (\tilde{G}, J)$ of $(\tilde{F}, I) = \hat{A}$ and $(\tilde{G}, J) = \hat{B}$ is both F-internal neutrosophic cubic soft set and F-external neutrosophic cubic soft set in X.

Theorem: 2.14

For any T-external neutrosophic cubic soft sets $(\tilde{F}, I) = \hat{A}$ and $(\tilde{G}, J) = \hat{B}$ in X, if $(\tilde{F}, I)^* = \hat{A}^*$ and $(\tilde{G}, J)^* = \hat{B}^*$ are T-internal neutrosophic cubic soft sets in X, then $(\tilde{F}, I) \cup_p (\tilde{G}, J)$ of $(\tilde{F}, I) = \hat{A}$ and $(\tilde{G}, J) = \hat{B}$ is a T-internal neutrosophic cubic soft sets in X.

Proof:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Consider, } (\tilde{F}, I) \cup_p (\tilde{G}, J) &= (\tilde{H}, C) \text{ where } C = I \cup J \\ \tilde{H}(e_i) &= \tilde{F}(e_i) \quad \text{if } e_i \in I - J \\ &= \tilde{G}(e_i) \quad \text{if } e_i \in J - I \\ &= \tilde{F}(e_i) \vee_p \tilde{G}(e_i) \quad \text{if } e_i \in I \cap J. \end{aligned}$$

Where $\tilde{F}(e_i) \vee_p \tilde{G}(e_i)$ is defined as,

$$\tilde{F}(e_i) \vee_p \tilde{G}(e_i) = \{ \langle x, r \max \{ A_{F_{e_i}}^+(x), B_{F_{e_i}}^-(x) \}, (\lambda_{F_{e_i}}(x) \vee \psi_{F_{e_i}}(x)) \rangle : x \in X \}, e_i \in I \cap J.$$

Assume that $(\tilde{F}, I)^* = \hat{A}^*$ and $(\tilde{G}, J)^* = \hat{B}^*$ are T-internal neutrosophic cubic soft sets in X for any T-external neutrosophic cubic soft sets $(\tilde{F}, I) = \hat{A}$ and $(\tilde{G}, J) = \hat{B}$ in X. Then,

$$\begin{aligned} \lambda_{T_{e_i}}(x) &\notin (A_{T_{e_i}}^-(x), A_{T_{e_i}}^+(x)), \psi_{T_{e_i}}(x) \notin (A_{T_{e_i}}^-(x), A_{T_{e_i}}^+(x)), \\ B_{T_{e_i}}^-(x) &\leq \lambda_{T_{e_i}}(x) \leq B_{T_{e_i}}^+(x), A_{T_{e_i}}^-(x) \leq \psi_{T_{e_i}}(x) \leq A_{T_{e_i}}^+(x), \end{aligned}$$

We now consider the following case,

- 1) $\lambda_{T_{e_i}}(x) \leq A_{T_{e_i}}^-(x) \leq \psi_{T_{e_i}}(x) \leq A_{T_{e_i}}^+(x)$, and $\psi_{T_{e_i}}(x) \leq B_{T_{e_i}}^-(x) \leq \lambda_{T_{e_i}}(x) \leq B_{T_{e_i}}^+(x)$,
- 2) $A_{T_{e_i}}^-(x) \leq \psi_{T_{e_i}}(x) \leq A_{T_{e_i}}^+(x) \leq \lambda_{T_{e_i}}(x)$, and $B_{T_{e_i}}^-(x) \leq \lambda_{T_{e_i}}(x) \leq B_{T_{e_i}}^+(x) \leq \psi_{T_{e_i}}(x)$,
- 3) $\lambda_{T_{e_i}}(x) \leq A_{T_{e_i}}^-(x) \leq \psi_{T_{e_i}}(x) \leq A_{T_{e_i}}^+(x)$, and $B_{T_{e_i}}^-(x) \leq \lambda_{T_{e_i}}(x) \leq B_{T_{e_i}}^+(x) \leq \psi_{T_{e_i}}(x)$,
- 4) $A_{T_{e_i}}^-(x) \leq \psi_{T_{e_i}}(x) \leq A_{T_{e_i}}^+(x) \leq \lambda_{T_{e_i}}(x)$, and $\psi_{T_{e_i}}(x) \leq B_{T_{e_i}}^-(x) \leq \lambda_{T_{e_i}}(x) \leq B_{T_{e_i}}^+(x)$,

First case implies that, $\psi_{T_{e_i}}(x) = A_{T_{e_i}}^-(x) = \lambda_{T_{e_i}}(x) = B_{T_{e_i}}^-(x)$,

Since, $(\tilde{F}, I)^* = \hat{A}^*$ and $(\tilde{G}, J)^* = \hat{B}^*$ are T-internal neutrosophic cubic soft sets in X, we have

$\psi_{T_{e_i}}(x) \leq A_{T_{e_i}}^+(x)$ and $\lambda_{T_{e_i}}(x) \leq B_{T_{e_i}}^+(x)$. It follows that,

$$\begin{aligned} (A_{T_{e_i}} \cup B_{T_{e_i}})^-(x) &= \max\{A_{T_{e_i}}^-(x), B_{T_{e_i}}^-(x)\} = (\lambda_{T_{e_i}}, \psi_{T_{e_i}})(x) \\ &\leq \max\{A_{T_{e_i}}^+(x), B_{T_{e_i}}^+(x)\} \\ &= (A_{T_{e_i}} \cup B_{T_{e_i}})^+(x) \quad \forall x \in X. \end{aligned}$$

Therefore P-union $(\tilde{F}, I) \cup_p (\tilde{G}, J)$ is a T-internal neutrosophic cubic soft set in X. We can prove the other cases by the similar to the first cases.

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